

THE ACTION OF HYDROGEN SULPHIDE ON AN AQUEOUS SOLUTION OF PARAPERIODIC ACID.

BY R. K. BAHL AND SURJIT SINGH.

The action of hydrogen sulphide on paraperiodic acid may be represented by the following two partial equations:—

The final equation is

or

The reaction starts according to the second equation after the first has been completed, *i e.*, after the whole of paraperiodic acid has been reduced to iodine.

In the course of a series of researches on the action of hydrogen sulphide on oxidising agents, such as chromates and permanganates, now in progress in this laboratory, attention was directed to its action on paraperiodic acid. Dunnicliff and his collaborators have also done work of a similar nature (Dunnicliff and Nijhawan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1; Dunnicliff and Soni, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 81; Dunnicliff and Kotwani, *ibid.*, 1931, 35, 3214).

Hydrogen sulphide was prepared from ferrous sulphide and hydrochloric acid and was purified as described by Dunnicliff and Kotwani (*loc. cit.*). Paraperiodic acid was prepared by Partington and Bahl's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1086).

Freshly prepared solution of paraperiodic acid (1%) of tested purity was used throughout. This reaction was not studied by bubbling the H_2S gas through the solution of paraperiodic acid as it resulted in the loss of free iodine liberated during the process.

A saturated solution of hydrogen sulphide in water was, therefore, added gradually to a solution of paraperiodic acid (1%). It resulted in the immediate liberation of free iodine and colloidal sulphur. The colour of the solution became deeper and deeper on account of the liberation of free iodine till a point was reached when the colour began to fade away and the solution turned milky.

The qualitative examination of the end-products obtained revealed the presence of (i) excess of free hydrogen sulphide, (ii) iodine ions due to the formation of hydroiodic acid, (iii) sulphate ions due to the presence of sulphuric acid and (iv) free sulphur which coagulated on standing.

The course of the reaction was investigated in stages. The products of the final stage differ from those of the initial stages in this respect that it contains hydroiodic acid, while the latter ones contain free iodine.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

A saturated solution of hydrogen sulphide was prepared by passing the purified gas through distilled water, kept cool at a constant temperature by surrounding the bottle with melting ice. This ensured a constant concentration of the gas in the solution throughout the work.

The Reactions in the Intermediate Stages.

20, 40, 60 and 80 c.c. respectively of the above saturated solution of hydrogen sulphide were added to each 100 c.c. of 1% solution of paraperiodic acid. The temperature was again kept constant as in the preparation of H₂S solution. The products of the reaction were estimated as follows.

Iodine.—Iodine was estimated by extracting it with carbon tetrachloride and then titrating it against thiosulphate solution, in the presence of a strong solution of potassium iodide. Free sulphur extracted by carbon tetrachloride along with the iodine does not interfere.

Sulphur.—Sulphur was determined by coagulating it from a fresh solution of the same sample by the addition of ammonium chloride. It was then collected over a glass gooch sinter (Bagster, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2631). Free iodine which settled along with the sulphur was washed out with potassium iodide solution.

Sulphuric acid was estimated as barium sulphate in the presence of an excess of hydrochloric acid, which dissolved any barium periodate formed by the action of barium chloride on unreacted paraperiodic acid.

Analytical results, given in Table I, are in agreement with the equation

The calculated values of sulphur for the stages A, B, and C are 9.99, 17.18 and 24.41% respectively, while those of sulphuric acid are 4.709, 8.095 and 11.502% respectively.

It is clear from Table I that the stage at which there is complete decomposition of the acid resulting in the complete liberation of iodine,

TABLE I.

Stage.	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
	Sat. soln. of H ₂ S added to 100 c. c. of 1% soln. of paraperiodic acid.	Sample No.	Iodine liberated.	Acid decomposed (Calc. from free I ₂).	Sulphur pptd.	BaSO ₄ formed.	H ₂ SO ₄ calc. from BaSO ₄ in column VI.
A.	20 c. c.	1	18.288%	32.832%	9.72%	11.18%	4.783%
		2	18.350	32.943	9.66	11.46	4.812
		3	18.288	32.932	9.70	11.00	4.649
			Mean 18.308	32.869	9.69	11.28	4.704
B.	40 c. c.	1	31.559	56.657	17.05	19.34	8.121
		2	31.496	56.544	17.56	19.28	8.096
		3	31.369	56.316	17.20	19.32	8.113
			Mean 31.474	56.505	17.27	19.31	8.110
C.	60 c. c.	1	44.96	79.850	24.50	27.62	11.598
		2	44.45	79.800	24.56	27.58	11.581
		3	45.23	81.200	24.38	27.96	11.732
			Mean 44.88	80.283	24.48	27.72	11.637
D.	80 c. c.	1	37.846	The whole of the acid has decomposed and I ₂ has been further partially reduced to HI.	34.66	31.00	13.017
		2	37.465		35.10	30.82	12.945
		3	38.100		34.78	31.50	13.228
			Mean 37.803		34.84	31.10	13.063

lies somewhere between C and D and that at D, a part of the free iodine gets reduced to hydroiodic acid with the precipitation of free sulphur.

The Final Stage.

The final stage was reached by further addition of the saturated solution of hydrogen sulphide. It was found that 84 c. c. of the solution were required to effect the complete reduction of 100 c. c. of 1% paraperiodic acid solution. However, an excess of the H S solution was used to ensure the completion of the reaction. The system at the end consisted of (i) free hydrogen sulphide, (ii) hydroiodic acid, (iii) sulphuric acid, and (iv) free sulphur.

The solution on standing resulted in the coagulation of sulphur which was estimated as before. Free hydrogen sulphide was removed from the filtrate by the addition of an excess of cadmium carbonate. Sulphuric acid was estimated as barium sulphate and iodine was determined as silver iodide.

TABLE II.

Sample No.	Iodine.	Sulphur ppted.	BaSO ₄ , formed.	H ₂ SO ₄ calc from BaSO ₄ .
1	55.290%	38.24%	31.02%	13.026%
2	55.540	38.10	31.40	13.185
3	55.469	37.46	31.48	13.218
4	55.361	37.84	31.42	13.194

These values agree with the equation

which requires I, 55.701 ; S, 37.42; and H₂SO₄, 14.32%.